

CONVERGENCE OF MATRIX MULTIPLE POWER SERIES

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Abstract: In this work, the regions of convergence of multiple power series with matrix arguments and their geometric properties are investigated. It is known that for single-variable matrix series the concept of the radius of convergence exists, whereas in the case of multiple series this concept has a much more complex character.

Keywords: Matrix series, multiple power series, matrix norm, absolute convergence.

1. Regions of Convergence

In this work

$$\sum_{k_1, \dots, k_n=0}^{\infty} A_{k_1, \dots, k_n} Z_1^{k_1} \dots Z_n^{k_n} = \sum_{k \geq 0} A_k Z^k \quad (1)$$

a series of this form is called a **matrix multiple power series**.

$$k = (k_1, \dots, k_n) \text{ multi-index.}$$

By the **absolute convergence** of the series

$$\sum_{k_1, \dots, k_n=0}^{\infty} \|A_{k_1, \dots, k_n}\| \|Z_1\|^{k_1} \dots \|Z_n\|^{k_n} \quad (2)$$

the convergence of the series is understood. Here $\|\cdot\| = \|\cdot\|_s$

For matrix multiple power series, **Abel's lemma** also holds.

Lemma 1 (Abel). If the series

$$Z^0 = (U_1^0 \Lambda_1^0 V_1^0, \dots, U_n^0 \Lambda_n^0 V_n^0) \in C^n [m \times m]$$

converges absolutely at some point

$$Z = (\zeta_1 \Lambda_1^0 \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \Lambda_n^0 \eta_n), \zeta_v, \eta_v \in \bar{\tau}, v = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

then this series converges absolutely and uniformly on the set of points

Definition 1. If the series $D \subset C^n [m \times m]$ converges absolutely in some domain, and does not converge in any larger domain containing it, then the domain **D** is called the **region of convergence** of the series. Using this definition,

Lemma 1 can also be stated in the following form: the region of convergence of the series $C^n[m \times m]$ is a **complete matrix Reinhardt domain** in the space.

The following natural question arises: **does an arbitrary complete matrix Reinhardt domain coincide with the region of convergence of some matrix multiple power series of the form?**

Below we show that the answer to this question is not affirmative, that is, in order for a domain to be a region of convergence, some additional conditions must also be satisfied.

2. Criterion for the convergence of a power series. Suppose that, $G \subset C^n[m \times m]$ - is a bounded domain [5]. We introduce the quantity

$$d_k(G) = \sup_{Z \in G} \|Z\|^k = \sup_{Z \in G} \|Z_1\|^{k_1} \cdots \|Z_n\|^{k_n}$$

which will later be of great importance, where k is a multi-index with nonnegative integer coordinates. The quantity $d_k(G)$ possesses the following simple properties:

1. If $G_1 \subset G_2$ then $d(G_1) \leq d(G_2)$.

2. If $pG = G_p$ - G is a homothety (deformation) of the domain with coefficient p with respect to zero, then $d_k(G_p) = p^{|k|} d_k(G)$, $|k| = k_1 + \dots + k_n$, holds.

3. $d_{kr}(G) = [d_k(G)]^r$, $kr = (k_1 r, \dots, k_n r)$, $r \geq 0$ - is an integer.

Theorem 1. For the series (1) to converge absolutely in the bounded complete matrix Reinhardt domain $G \subset C^n[m \times m]$

$$\sum_{k \geq 0} A_k d_k(G) Z^k \quad (3)$$

it is necessary and sufficient that the series $T = \underbrace{\tau \times \dots \times \tau}_n$ converges absolutely in the matrix polydisc.

Proof. (Necessity). Assume that $0 < p < 1$ va $pG = G_p$ - G is a homothety (deformation) of the domain with coefficient p with respect to zero. Since $G_p \subset\subset G$ there exist a number $r > 1$ and a bounded complete matrix

Reinhardt domain $G_r = r \cdot G_p$ such that $G_p \subset G_r \subset\subset G$ holds. In \bar{G}_r the series

(1) converges absolutely, while the series (2) is an ordinary power series.

Therefore, according to the theorem in [1], there exists a number M such that,

$$\|A_k\| d_k(G_r) \leq M \quad (4)$$

the inequality holds.

$$\sum_{k \geq 0} \|A_k\| d_k(G_p) \leq M \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{d_k(G_p)}{d_k(G_{rp})} = M \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{d_k(G_p)}{r^{|k|} d_k(G_p)} = M \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{1}{r^{|k|}} < \infty$$

That is,

$$\sum_{k \geq 0} \|A_k\| d_k(G_p)$$

The series converges. On the other hand,

$$\sum_{k \geq 0} \|A_k\| d_k(G_p) = \sum_{k \geq 0} \rho^{|k|} d_k(G) \quad (5)$$

Thus, the series (3) converges absolutely at all $0 < p < 1$ of the skeleton of the polydisc $T_p = \tau_p \times \dots \times \tau_p$. Here

$$\tau_\rho = \{Z_\nu \in \mathbb{C}[m \times m] : Z_\nu Z_\nu^* < \rho^2 I, \nu = 1, \dots, n\}$$

Then, according to **Lemma 1**, the series (3) converges absolutely in the whole T .

Proof. (Sufficiency). If the series (3) converges absolutely in T , then this series also converges absolutely on the skeleton [2] $T_p, 0 < p < 1$. Therefore, the series (5) converges. Let Z be an arbitrary point of $G_p = pG$. Then:

$$\left\| \sum_{k \geq 0} A_k Z^k \right\| \leq \sum_{k \geq 0} \|A_k\| \|Z\|^k \leq \sum_{k \geq 0} \|A_k\| \sup_{Z \in G_p} \|Z\|^k = \sum_{k \geq 0} \|A_k\| d_k(G_p) < \infty$$

Hence, the series (1) converges absolutely in G_p . Using the arbitrariness of $p, 0 < p < 1$ we obtain the absolute convergence of the series (1) in G .

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